

1 NLRP10 functions during transformation and development.

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7 We previously described NLRP10 expression in cellular contexts indicative of high speed of cycling. We
8 describe here expression of NLRP10 during transformation and embryonic development. NLRP10 was
9 activated by the SV40 transgene and by expression of the C-raf and Myc oncogenes *in vivo* in the embryo.
10 Accordingly, inhibition of Braf *in vitro* resulted in silencing of NLRP10. In the embryo, NLRP10 expression
11 was controlled by the p63 tumor suppressor transcription factor and expressed in a stage-specific fashion
12 in the developing heart. NLRP10 activation during transformation *in vivo* was associated with expression
13 of Igf1, Bmp1, the mTOR component Rictor and the stem cell marker CD44. The data together indicated
14 that NLRP10 possesses functions during transformation of solid tissues that reflect a function for NLRP10
15 during embryonic development.
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